

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Izzatullayev L.A.

ADVANTAGES OF ADJUSTABLE TECHNOLOGIES AND COTTON PRODUCTIVITY

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/OKTABR

